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Data Review

Data Citation

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Abstract

The dataset was compiled for the PhD project 'Far-right Mobilisation in Hybrid Regimes: Explaining patterns of protest in Georgia and Ukraine' by Tamta Gelashvili. It provides systematic information on far-right–organized public events, including the protest organizer, issues, location, and number of participants, in two post-Soviet hybrid regimes. The dataset covers Georgia (2003–2020) and Ukraine (2004–2020). It is available through the web portal of the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research (Sikt) after creating an account and submitting a data access request.

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Review of the dataset ‘Far-right Social Movements in Georgia and Ukraine’

by Stas Gorelik

The dataset was compiled for the PhD project ‘Far-right Mobilisation in Hybrid Regimes: Explaining patterns of protest in Georgia and Ukraine’ by Tamta Gelashvili, and provides a systematic protest-event analysis (PEA) of far-right organized public events in two post-Soviet hybrid regimes. The dataset covers two countries: Georgia (from 2003 to 2020) and Ukraine (from 2004 to 2020). The unit of analysis is a single protest event, defined as a public, contentious act occurring within a 24-hour period in a specific city or area with largely consistent aims and participants.

For Georgia, the database records 154 far-right protest events between 2003 and 2020, drawn from media sources (in that case, a selected Georgian online newspaper, Netgazeti). For Ukraine, events were coded from the national news agency UNIAN; over 4,000 news articles were reviewed to identify 560 far-right protest events during 2004-2020.

Key variables include date, location, number of participants, main organizer(s), target(s), event type (demonstrative, confrontational, violent), presence of police or counterprotest, and thematic issue. The database thereby enables longitudinal and cross-national analysis of far-right mobilization strategies, their temporal dynamics and variation across two national contexts.

Nevertheless, several important limitations exist. First, the reliance on media coverage as the primary data source means that events not reported in the press are missing from the dataset, introducing the possibility of selection bias (particularly for smaller protests). Second, and relatedly, although event coding follows a systematic protocol, the measurement of key variables, such as estimated crowd size or the presence of violence, rests on journalistic accounts and may be subject to under- or over-reporting. Third, representativeness across time and space may vary: shifts in media freedom, editorial priorities, or newsworthiness can affect which protests receive coverage, complicating the interpretation of temporal or cross-contextual trends.

Data access: The dataset must be ordered through Surveybanken ([link](#) to the dataset), after registering with this data repository. Link to the dataset on Surveybanken: <https://surveybanken.sikt.no/en/study/05a2d8eb-edd0-4c56-86df-58e3bc4588d6/8?type=studyMetadata&datafileCheck=done>.

Related publications:

- Gelashvili, T. (2023). “Opportunities Matter: The Evolution of Far-Right Protest in Georgia.” *Europe-Asia Studies*, 75(4), 649-674.
- Gelashvili, T. (2024). “Political Opportunities and Mobilisation on the Far-Right in Ukraine.” *East European Politics*, 40(2), 277-298.